

Information sheet 1.14

Heat and cold treatments

This information sheet is a supporting document to Appendix A ('Standardised checklist of risk reduction options') of the Guidance of the EFSA Plant Health Panel on quantitative pest risk assessment.

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A. Description of the RROs

Heat and cold treatments aim to kill or inactivate pests (all life stages or not) in a number of matrices: plants, plants for planting, plant products for food and feed uses (as such or after processing), in soil or growing media, in wood packaging material, on tools or in facilities. Such treatments can be applied to all types of pests: arthropods, nematodes, virus and virus-like organisms, bacteria, fungi; they may affect all life stages or only certain stages. Such treatments can be applied in the country of origin, at destination or during transport.

Treatment schedules should kill or inactivate, during an appropriate time period, the target pest without causing any unacceptable prejudice to the treated material itself.

Exposure to heat may be air or water mediated, at atmospheric pressure or at higher pressure (autoclaving). Heat can kill or inactivate certain pests, its effectiveness depends on the practical conditions of implementation (duration, presence or absence of water) and on the material subjected to the treatment (phenotypic stage, thickness...). In all cases, such a treatment can be efficient only if all parts of the submitted plant material are exposed to a temperature above a minimum during a long enough lapse of time.

Exposure to cold temperature is most often applied in cold rooms and is air mediated. Temperatures may be positive or negative (above or below 0° C).

- Autoclaving

Autoclaving consists in exposing plant products (not destined to plantation) or tools to hot saturated water vapor in a specially designed container kept under pressure.

The exposure to hot water vapor during a sufficient period of time may kill or inactivate all plant pests. The effectiveness of this technique may vary depending on the material to be treated (porosity...) and its thickness.

- Steam treatment

Steam treatment consists of injecting water-saturated steam at atmospheric pressure or under vacuum in growing media or of exposing plant products (most often not destined to plantation), or tools or material, to hot water steam.

The contact of the steam with the material to be treated for a given period may kill or inactivate all plant pests. The effectiveness of this technique may vary depending on the material to be treated and its cleanness for instance.

Protocols for steam treatments of a number of plant products (rice straw, tobacco, logs and firewood), equipment and facilities can be found in the USDA Treatment manual.

A protocol for hot steam treatment of coniferous bark has been developed in Portugal for the elimination of the pinewood nematode (Fonseca *et al.*, 2013).

- Hot water treatment

Hot water treatment consists in dipping plants for planting or plant products in an open tank plenty of water, at a given temperature, for a given duration, at atmospheric pressure. When the temperature / duration scale is fulfilled, plant material is removed from the tank, drained and let for drying. The procedure can easily be standardised so that results are reliable, easy to monitor and to trace back.

- Hot air treatment

Hot air treatment is operated similarly to hot water treatment, but exposure to heat is simply operated in an air heated cabinet. The humidity of that air may be adjusted.

Dry air is less effective than water or water saturated steam to kill or inactivate plant pests. This is partly due to the fact that transfer of heat from air to plant material is slower than water / steam mediated heat transfer. In addition, water itself has a role in hot water disinfection, which is not the case for air. As a consequence hot air treatment is no longer used for sterilisation of tools used for human and animal surgery, or for sterilisation of food chains.

Vapor Heat (VH) and Forced Hot Air (FHA) treatments use heated air to warm fruit to temperatures that are lethal to target pests, primarily fruit flies. Generally, VH treatment differs from FHA only in the relative humidity of the air in the treatment chamber; higher humidity levels may preserve fruit quality (USDA, Treatment manual).

- Cold treatment

Cold treatment consists of exposing plants or plant products to cold temperatures that are lethal to pests. Exposure to cold temperatures is often rather long, thus the method can generally be applied to plant material whatever its thickness is (time allows low temperature to reach all parts of the treated plant material). An appropriate control of the ambient humidity may be important for the effectiveness of the treatment and the resulting quality of the treated plant material.

Cold treatment is routinely applied for fruit during transport as it prevents fruit deterioration.

The following internationally recognised standards are applicable for heat or cold treatments.

- ISPM 15,
- USDA Treatment manual,
- EPPO Standards.

Table 1: Target organisms of the RROs

Plant pests	RROs				
	autoclaving	steam	hot water	hot air	cold
insects, mites	X	X	X	X	X
fungi	X	X	X		
bacteria	X	X	X		
nematodes	X	X	X		
virus, virus like organisms	X	X	X		
plants (including seeds)	X	X			

Table 2: Target commodities of the RROs

material	RROs				
	autoclaving	steam	hot water	hot air	cold
germplasms (other than seeds)			x	x	x
plant part for multiplication			x	x	x
plantlets for planting			x	x	
seeds for seedling / bulbs...			x	x	x
plant material for food / feed uses	x			x	x
plant material for ornamental uses (cut flowers, leaves...)					x
wood, packaging material, bark	x	x		x	
growing media, soil	x	x			
facilities, pots, supports, tools...	x	x			
plant material for other uses (industry...)	x			x	x
fruit			x	x	x

B. Risk factors

The relevant pathways may be:

- trade of plants for planting,
- trade of plant products for food and feed,
- trade of plant product for non-food / non-feed uses,
- trade of growing media,
- packaging material.

The use of the described RROs reduces the likelihood of survival of pests acting on their prevalence in association with consignments.

The described RROs act on the entry step only.

Table 3: Point of application of measures

Points where measures may be effective	RROs				
	autoclaving	steam	hot water	hot air	cold
Post-harvest treatment	x	x	x	x	x
During transport					x
At place of destination	x	x	x	x	x

C. Parameters to consider regarding effectiveness of the RRO

For plant material or growing media or packaging / handling material or machinery that can support heat or cold treatments (appropriate plant species and life stages for instance) and that react well to the treatment, the effectiveness of heat or cold treatments depends on the combination of temperature and duration. A minimum (heat treatment) or a maximum (cold treatment) temperature (in the depth of the material to be treated or on surface for non-porous packaging/handling material), a minimum duration and a minimum combination of both parameters are essential. One should notice that excessive temperatures may have detrimental effects. The mean (air or water mediation) to expose the material to be treated is also determining.

A lapse of time is necessary for the entire plant parts or porous handling/packaging material to reach the appropriate temperature, so most often only thin enough material can be efficiently treated, except when treatment can be long enough.

A good control of the temperature and time parameters is essential for the effectiveness of the treatment (USDA Treatment manual).

Heat and cold treatments require specific equipment that is generally expensive (investment and running costs), they are not available everywhere, and treatments may take time. It may be difficult to heat-treat huge quantities of material.

Not all plant material can be submitted to heat or cold treatments, not all plant life stages can benefit from heat or cold treatments.

1. General parameters to consider regarding effectiveness of heat and cold treatments

- Factors that can increase the effectiveness of heat / cold treatments

Treating plant material at physiological stages when they are less susceptible to hot or cold temperatures may allow increasing the acceptable applied temperature / time scale, which may result in a better effectiveness to kill or inactivate pests.

When used for disinfection / decontamination of plant products not intending for planting or for facilities / pieces of equipment, heat treatment is more effective on previously washed or cleaned materials as transfer of heat is easier and quicker.

As heat transfers take some time, it is easier to treat products that allow a quick and effective transfer of heat. As specific heat of water is higher compared to specific heat of air, water mediated heat treatments are preferred when possible.

- Factors that may decrease, alter or jeopardise the effectiveness of heat / cold treatments

Treating plant material at physiological stages they are more susceptible to hot or cold temperatures obliges to reduce the applied temperature / time scale, which may result in a lower effectiveness to kill or inactivate pests.

When used for disinfection / decontamination of plant products not intending for planting or for facilities / pieces of equipment, heat treatment is made less effective on dirty surfaces.

A temperature too low, a treatment duration too short, a combination of temperature and duration not adapted, a level of humidity not suitable (when applicable), plant parts too thick to allow a proper diffusion of temperature, too porous packaging or handling material are generally key elements that may jeopardize the effectiveness of heat / cold treatments.

The treatment of products that poorly conducts heat is less effective, except if contact time can be expanded.

- Factors that may make heat / cold treatments counter-productive

Applying heat or cold treatments may reduce the natural flora present for instance on fruit or growing media, making (re)colonization by pests easier.

- Factors that may make the efficiency of heat / cold treatments more difficult to assess or to check by importing countries

Most often, material submitted to heat or cold treatments do not show any specific aspect that can be recognised by border inspectors. Nevertheless, traceability of such treatments done on consignments is rather easy to document and to obtain.

2. Specific parameters to consider regarding the effectiveness of the autoclaving

The hotter and the longer is the autoclaving, the best is its efficiency to kill or inactivate pests. But excesses may alter the technological quality of the treated material. Autoclaving porous material is very effective providing water vapour can easily enter the porosity.

Autoclaving of growing media is very effective but leads to very poor micro flora, which may alter their quality or facilitate further colonisation by undesirable organisms.

3. Specific parameters to consider regarding the effectiveness of the steam treatment

Steam treatment is by nature short and is very effective on clean surfaces. Porous materials or dirty surfaces provide heat protection to pests and make that treatment less effective.

A special case is the steam treatment of growing media that is arranged in dedicated equipment so that enough hot steam can be injected where the pests can be. Steaming of growing media is effective but leads to very poor micro flora, which may alter their quality or facilitate further colonisation by undesirable organisms.

4. Specific parameters to consider regarding the effectiveness of the hot water treatment

It is advisable to pre-heat planting material in the storage facility before the hot water treatment and to cool them down slowly after treatment in order to prevent damages.

Treating previously washed or cleaned planting material may make hot water treatment more effective. Potted plants for instance cannot be submitted to hot water treatment. If appropriate pesticides, stable at the target temperature, are available and registered for such a use, they can be applied as a bath treatment, increasing the effectiveness of the hot water treatment.

Hot treatment cannot be applied to all plant species and varieties as some are physiologically altered by the treatment and lose their commercial interest.

5. Specific parameters to consider regarding the effectiveness of the hot air treatment

Plant material should be exposed to heated air long enough to allow heat to reach all parts.

Increasing temperature, or duration, or combination of temperature and duration, may lead to unacceptable alterations of the physical characteristics or of the physiology of the treated plant material. Heat treatment may be applied to improve quality of some woods.

6. Specific parameters to consider regarding the effectiveness of the cold treatment

Treating plant material at physiological stages they are less susceptible to cold may permit to increase the acceptable applied temperature/time scale, which may result in a better effectiveness to kill or inactivate pests.

Exposure of the commodity to a controlled atmosphere for a short period (e.g., 24 h) previous to the cold treatment can increase its effectiveness (e.g., Alonso et al., 2005a, b).

Temperature requirements should be defined according to lethal temperatures for the pest.

Cold treatment can induce physiological changes that make some pests more difficult to detect in consignments (for instance bacteria that may enter a viable but non-culturable status).

D. Applicability / feasibility of the RRO

1. Practical feasibility of the RROs

Heat and treatments are generally to be applied at appropriate time, depending for instance on the life stage or on the availability of heat / cold treatment units, often it is well before the final destination of the plant material is known. It may therefore not always be possible to provide treated material when orders come late in the season. This is nevertheless not the case for fruit treatment (done during packaging at a moment when destination is normally known) or wood treatments (that can be done

with no physiological constraints) for instance. Hot water treatment can even be applied in the country of destination.

Heat treatments entail direct and indirect costs for producers or traders (investment, running costs, energy needs, time for handling...) that may make production non-profitable. It may also disqualify the production for certain markets or lead to a decrease of price paid to the producer.

Limitations of feasibility that can be anticipated	RROs				
	autoclaving	steam	hot water	hot air	cold
technical limitations	x	x	x	x	x
availability of equipment / facilities	x	x	x	x	x
cost limitations	x	x	x	x	x
timing possibilities	x	x			

Major limitations of feasibility that can be anticipated

2. Applicability / feasibility of autoclaving as an agricultural practice

This method cannot be applied to plant for planting material as living cells do not survive to the treatment. It can be applied to non-porous material, but also to porous material providing that water saturated atmosphere can penetrate all cavities. The time exposure shall take into consideration the specific heat value of the material to be sterilized. The procedure is easily standardized and quality standards are easy to implement for reliable results. It is easy to monitor a treatment and to trace it back for quality concerns.

In the agricultural sector, autoclaving consists mainly in applying heat to wooden made packaging material exposed in an enclosure to a water saturated atmosphere, at a pressure higher than the normal atmospheric pressure, during a given duration. To be efficient, the treatment shall be done in specific equipment, in the absence of air. This treatment kills all plant pests, providing the temperature / duration scale is adapted to the thickness of the material to be treated.

Too high temperatures may alter the physical properties of the treated materials. The treatment may alter the physical appearance of the treated material (wood becoming greenish for instance) and change its physical properties.

Special costly pieces of equipment are requested, energy is needed to heat water and generate a water saturated atmosphere.

Autoclaving may alter the aspect of wood and therefore may reduce its price. It may even prevent treated wood pieces from certain final uses (furniture...).

3. Applicability / feasibility of steam treatment

Too high temperatures and/or too long exposure may kill the plant material submitted to steam treatment. Therefore, steaming can mainly be applied for surface disinfection of plant parts that are thick enough and protected by external layers that do not suffer from heat. That is for instance the case for bulbs. The exposure temperature / time scale is crucial to achieve disinfection without killing the plant material.

Special equipment and energy are needed for steaming and may make the method too costly for many routine matters. Nevertheless, steaming is used in agriculture.

Steaming is highly effective to decontaminate equipment and facilities that resist to water and heat (metal, non-porous concrete, some synthetic materials...) and are not or poorly porous. It may nevertheless alter the physical properties of some of the treated non-living materials and therefore limit the range of equipment and facilities that can be steam disinfected. The killing factor is temperature so only rather clean surfaces can be effectively disinfected. Surfaces covered by a thick layer of dirt for instance cannot be effectively disinfected that way.

Steaming of growing media is used for some crops soilless grown under glasshouses. Nevertheless, steaming may result in alterations of their physical structure, in the release of chemical compounds

(heavy metals...) and in modifications of the soil micro flora, which may be detrimental for plants. This lead to special care when using steam disinfected growing media.

Difficulties to treat effectively a thick enough layer of soil, cost and running costs of dedicated equipment and impacts on the structure and chemical and microbiological composition of soils make the method hardly useful for open fields. Nevertheless, steaming may be used to surface sterilize soil in glasshouses or screen houses that aim to grow plant soilless (with a plastic drop cloth to isolate the culture from soil).

4. Applicability / feasibility of hot water treatment

Certain plant species or varieties, certain plants for planting may be more susceptible to hot water treatments, which may imply that treated material could not behave strictly similarly than untreated ones (phenotypic alterations...). This could prevent customers to buy hot water treated plants for planting.

Hot water treatment can normally be done only on thin or small plant parts, even if the treatment is also recommended for mango fruit as insect eggs or larvae are located near the surface. Otherwise, excessive scale of temperature / duration of exposure of external parts of the planting material should be necessary to achieve disinfestation, but it may lead to unacceptable alteration of the physiology of the plants for planting (death, changes of the main phenotypic characteristics of the variety...). Physiological susceptibility to hot water treatment may vary according to plant species, plant cultivars and phenological stage of the plant material. In practice, only dormant or dormant woody plant material (twigs or rooted non-potted young plants without leaves, dormant bulbs, and seeds) and some fruits can be submitted to hot water treatment. Hot water treatment is therefore not adapted to all pests and all plant parts, at all life stages. All plant species cannot be submitted to such a treatment.

Hot water treatment is already routinely used for instance for grapevine plant for planting material (twigs). It guaranties that grapevine for planting material is free from flavescence dorée, for instance. A rather long acquired experience indicates that the method is effective and reliable, at least for some plant species / pests combinations.

Special equipment is necessary to apply the hot water treatment. The cost and running costs of such equipment is not particularly high but as it is not used often or for large quantities of plant material, the investment is hardly economically profitable. It may be difficult to find an adequate service provider.

5. Applicability / feasibility of hot air treatment

Hot air treatment can be done only on thin or small plant parts. Otherwise, excessive scale of temperature / duration of exposure of external parts of the planting material should be necessary to achieve disinfection / disinfestation, but it may lead to unacceptable alteration of the physiology of the plant for planting material (death, changes of the main phenotypic characteristics of the variety...).

Hot air treatment is less efficient than hot water one because heat transfer is slower.

Special equipment is necessary to apply the hot air treatment as facilities that can easily be heated are required. Those facilities shall permit homogenous heat dispersal. The cost and running costs of such equipment is not particularly high but as it is not used often or for large quantities of plant material, the investment is hardly economically profitable. It may be difficult to find an adequate service provider.

6. Applicability / feasibility of cold treatment

Cold treatment requires adequate facilities to store consignments at the requested temperature. Such facilities are rather common for positive temperature (a little bit above 0°C) but less common for negative temperatures.

Running costs for such facilities may be high, especially in countries where energy costs are high.

Cold treatment may be applied during transport in refrigerated cargos.

E. Other RROs that may lead to similar effects

1. Autoclaving

Autoclaving of growing media can be replaced by steam treatment.
For wood, fumigation or irradiation may replace autoclaving.

2. Steam treatment

Steam cleaning of machinery or of handling material can be replaced by (high pressure hot) water cleaning with appropriate disinfectants.
Steam treatment of growing media may be replaced by autoclaving or irradiation, but costs are much higher.

3. Hot water treatment

For certain pests and certain plant material (e.g. woody plant stems and eggs of insects), hot water treatment may be replaced by pesticide application.

4. Hot air treatment

In some cases, hot air treatments may be replaced by application of pesticides or irradiation.

5. Cold treatment

In some cases, cold treatments may be replaced by application of pesticides or irradiation.

F. Combinations of RROs that include these RROs

Heat treatments are most often single measures not applied in combination with others.

Plant for planting material intended for hot water treatment shall nevertheless be in good health to take heat, therefore a preliminary selection of healthy material is necessary.

Cold treatments may be part of a systems approach including measures such as areas of low pest prevalence (e.g. ISPM 35 Systems approach for pest risk management of fruit flies (Tephritidae))

G. Conclusion

Synoptic table for the RROs

Target	area of application	expected effect	main technical limitations of use	RROs with similar effects / most often in combination
Autoclaving				
all kind of pests	Consignments that are not intended for planting or that do not suffer from hot temperature / moisture / pressure	Reduce prevalence of pests	Costs, tolerance of the consignment to such physical treatment	
Steam treatment				
Facilities, machineries, tools	Heat / moisture resistance needed	Reduce prevalence of pests		
Growing media	Material that allow steam to penetrate	Reduce prevalence of pests		
Hot water treatment				
All pests	Plant material that can support water and heat	Reduce prevalence of pests		Chemical control with thermostable water soluble pesticides
Hot air treatment				
All pests	Plant material that can support heat	Reduce prevalence of pests		
Cold treatment				
Insects, mites	Plant material that can support cold temperatures			

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